

ESSENTIAL THEORIES OF PROPER NAMES

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Annotation

The following article demonstrates the former and crucial different theories about proper names which were signified and emphasized by linguists and scientists. There are still obvious and weak proper names theories exist in the science. It is difficult to distinguish all of them but some important theories are illustrated in the article.

Key words: proper names, theories, logical approach, linguists, denotative meaning, connotative meaning.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada atoqli otlar yuzasidan turli xil olimlar tomonidan ilgari surilgan dastlabki va muhim nazariyalar keltirib o'tilgan. Hozirda tilshunoslik sohasida ushbu mavzu yuzasidan aniq va o'z isbotini topmagan nazariyalar juda ham ko'p. Mavzu doirasida keltirib o'tilgan nazariyalarning barchasini ifodalash ilojisiz, ammo ularning asosiy va fanda muhim o'rin kasb etgan nazariyalar mazkur maqolada o'z ifodasini topgan.

Kalir so'zlar: atoqli ot, nazariyalar, mantiqiy yondashuv, tilshunoslar, denonativ, konnotativ ma'nolar.

Аннотация

В данной статье представлены первоначальные и важнейшие теории, выдвинутые различными учеными в отношении имен собственных. В настоящее время в области языкознания существует множество неточных и недоказанных теорий по этой теме. Невозможно охватить все теории, рассматриваемые в рамках данной проблематики, однако основные и наиболее значимые для науки концепции нашли свое отражение в этой статье.

Ключевые слова: имя собственное, теории, логический подход, лингвисты, денотативные, коннотативные значения.

Throughout the past century, proper nouns and anthroponyms were considered not only a linguistic topic, but also a subject of logic and philosophy, and in the past, scholars of logic and philosophy also conducted research on anthroponyms. According to the opinions of logicians, a horse consists of proper nouns and related nouns. The first thoughts on this matter can be found in the works of ancient scholars and philosophers.

One of the well-known English philosophers who conducted the first research on proper nouns is John Stuart Mill (1806-1874). John Stuart Mill's research theories are one of the most common theories in English linguistics. Although Mill was not known as a linguist, scientists were able to form the concept of a proper noun using his work on proper nouns. In his opinion, each name signifies some object. Proper nouns do not have any meaning, but they have a sign and feature that distinguishes the object (nouns) from each other. He believes that there is no connection between the signs and properties of proper nouns and their meaning, that is, they do not have a connotative meaning, but only have a denotative meaning. "Nouns have no connotative meaning, in short, they do not give any meaning." The scientist divides nouns into two classes: connotative and non-connotative classes. Unlike connotative nouns, nouns that do not have a connotative meaning "do not express any attribute (uniqueness) about the objects to which they are designated and function as a denotative linguistic unit" (a theory that contradicts the scientist's opinion), "Nouns that do not have a connotative meaning, in short, do not mean any meaning" [J. Mill 1874, 32].

The English linguist H. Joseph disagrees with J. Mill's opinion that personal names do not have denotation and signification, and emphasizes that this opinion is "completely incorrect." "Personal names are signs that guide our thoughts towards a specific person. This sign, of course, carries meaning" [Joseph, 1946, p. 151]. According to the scholar, a proper noun has more meaning than a common noun, because even if a proper noun does not fully reflect all the characteristics of a person, it indicates a characteristic that describes the person from its meaning. In particular, personal names can provide partial information about a person's nationality, nature, profession, even if this information is not always accurate.

Some of the theories about proper nouns by another English linguist, Nicolaisen, do not align with John Stuart Mill's ideas. In his scientific work "Are there connotative meanings," in contrast to J. Mill's theory, he also emphasizes that proper nouns have connotative meanings. In his treatise, he quotes the following: "When we mention a proper name, such as Brown or Smith, or the name of a city like York, we certainly convey to the listener some meaning associated with these names, in addition to the names themselves." The author also emphasizes that extralinguistic factors in proper nouns influence onomastic meaning. ("connotative proper names do exist, as a part of a socially, culturally, historically, and individually fashioned onomasticon") [Nicolaisen, 1978: 45, 47].

In this context, we will cite the opinion of the Russian linguist A.V. Superanskaya on this topic: "It is generally recognized that in every language there exists a special class of proper nouns that stands in opposition to common nouns." Another perspective regarding proper nouns is that "Proper nouns are a vivid mirror of every nation; their individual or collective meanings are directly related to the history and culture of that nation."

According to the Belgian linguist Et Beussens, proper nouns function as substitutes for other language units and do not convey a specific meaning {Buysens, 1938, 112}. Danish scholar Paul Christophersen equates proper nouns to the numbers given to prisoners. No matter how similar they may be, the same number is not assigned. They are identified by numbers but not described. Similarly, the English name "Smith" (meaning blacksmith) can be applied not only to people in this profession but also to women. This is the unit that identifies Mr. Smith, which consists of a sequence of sounds {Christophersen, 1939, 64}.

These studies challenge theories that have been accepted for centuries regarding proper nouns and common nouns belonging to the noun word class. Theories that emerge within the logical framework of language are typically characterized differently. For instance, some scholars consider proper nouns to belong to auxiliary word classes based on their semantic markers, while others prefer to classify proper nouns with a special dictionary, calling them strict identifiers due to the uniqueness of their meaning. A third group of scholars argue that proper nouns do not belong to the lexical category and thus are not included among general words. They propose that proper nouns should be placed in a special word class or a separate category. Despite the characteristics inherent to proper nouns, all these views categorize proper nouns as words without meaning. Consequently, the problem of the semantic content of names primarily leads to the issue of name reference, which can be implemented in two ways: direct and indirect indication. Proper nouns are incompletely formed common nouns and incomplete generic nouns that lack associative and structural connections along the semantic meaning line.

According to researchers, the logical approach has become one of the most effective methods in studying proper nouns. This approach illuminates the essence of proper nouns by comparing them with common nouns, often through contrast. As a result of this comparative analysis, it has become evident that the main distinguishing feature between proper nouns and common nouns is their content and possession of specific lexical meanings.

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